

Problem Domain Analysis and Development Process in MDDPlatform: An Online Ordering System Example

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This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This document presents complementary materials that describe the end-to-end model-driven development process within MDDPlatform. It begins with a problem domain analysis using the CRAC metamodel, addressing order, customer, product, and shopping cart subdomains. It then details the proposed model-driven development and code generation processes, followed by a demonstration of the approach through an online ordering system example. Together, these sections illustrate how problem analysis and process design are systematically operationalized into a real-world software solution.

1. An Experiment: MDDPlatform in Action

In this section, we develop a part of the online ordering system using our proposed method. We selected this example for our case study and experiment, and we will detail it in subsequent section. We will outline the models developed across various abstraction levels and demonstrate how they are refined through the transformation patterns and functionalities available in MDDPlatform, evolving into CIM, PIM, PSM, and Code models. Additionally, we will illustrate the high-level view where DomainModels and ModelTransformations microservices collaborate to invoke these transformation patterns, transforming the input models into the output models.

1.1. Proposed MDD Process for Experiment

To create a model-driven software, the execution of transformations and refining the models can be defined in a high-level process. MDDPlatform provides the ability to define model-driven processes using model transformation patterns. To save time for participants in this experiment, a sample model-driven process has been defined as default, which users can use. This process, which we call Model-Driven Development Process, consists of 5 phases: 1) Initial Phase, 2) CIM Models Construction, 3) PIM Models Construction, 4) PSM Models Construction, and 5) Code Generation. The details of the first 4 phases are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The details of the MDD process designed for the experiment

Phase	Activity	Task
Initial Phase	Explore Problem Domain	Manage CRAC Workshop
		Create <u>CRAC Models</u>
CIM Models Construction	CIM to CIM Model Transformation	Map 'DomainConcept' of CRAC Model to 'DomainConcept' of CIM Model
		Map 'DomainConcept' Responsibilities to 'DomainConcept' Operations
		Describe 'DomainConcept' Properties in the CIM Model
		Convert Relation with Primitive ValueObject to the Concept Property
		Convert Association with Complex Type to the Concept Relation
PIM Models Construction	Transform CIM Models to PIM Models	Convert CRAC Model to CQRS Model from 'CommandHandler' Perspective
		Convert CRAC Model to CQRS Model from 'EventHandler' Perspective
		Map 'DomainConcept' Responsibility to the 'Command' Dispatched By 'ApiController'
	Refine CQRS Model at the PIM Level of Abstraction	Define Properties of Commands & Events in the CQRS Model
		Define CommandHandler & EventHandler Collaborators
		Replace Relation With Property in the CQRS Model from 'Event' Perspective
		Replace Relation With Property in the CQRS Model from 'Command' Perspective
		Create 'Handle' Method of 'CommandHandler' in the CQRS Model

Phase	Activity	Task	
		Create 'Handle' Method of 'EventHandler' in the CQRS Model	
		Create 'CommandHandler' Constructor in the CQRS Model	
		Create 'EventHandler' Constructor in the CQRS Model	
	Refine ApiController Model at the PIM Level of Abstraction	Convert Dispatched Command to the ApiController Endpoint	
		Set the Values of the Endpoint Properties	
		Convert ApiController Endpoints to the Operation & Attributes	
	Merge PIM & CIM Core Domain Entities	Describe Design-Specific Concerns of Core Domain	
		Set Relational Dimension Between PIM & CIM Model	
		Merge CIM Concepts With PIM Core Domain	
	PSM Models Construction	Transform PIM Models to PSM Models	Map PIM Controller Model to PSM Controller Model from 'ApiController' Perspective
Map PIM Controller Model to PSM Controller Model From 'Interface' Perspective			
Map PIM Controller Model to PSM Controller Model From 'Service' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model from 'Command' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model from 'CommandHandler' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model from 'Event' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model from 'EventHandler' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model From 'Interface' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model From 'Service' Perspective			
Map PIM CQRS Model to PSM CQRS Model From 'Repository' Perspective			
Map PIM Core Domain Model to PSM Core Domain Model			
Refine PSM Controller Model and Merge with PIM Controller Model			Describe Implementation-Specific Concerns of Controllers
			Set Relational Dimension Between PSM & PIM Controller Models
		Merge PIM & PSM Controller Models	
		Import Using Packages of Controller Model	
Refine PSM CQRS Model and Merge with PIM CQRS Model		Describe Implementation-Specific Concerns of CQRS Model	
		Set Relational Dimension Between PSM & PIM CQRS Models	
		Merge PIM & PSM CQRS Models	
		Import Using Packages of CQRS Model	
Refine PSM Core Domain Model and Merge With PIM Core Domain Model		Describe Implementation-Specific Concerns of Core Domain Model	

Phase	Activity	Task
		Set Relational Dimension Between PSM & PIM Core Domain Models
		Merge PIM & PSM Core Domain Models
		Import Using Packages of Core Domain Model
	Refine PSM Repository Model	Describe Implementation-Specific Concerns of Repositories
		Create Repository Operation
		Set Repository Operation Body
	Refine PSM Interface Model	Map Interface Property to Concept Attribute in CQRS Model
		Extract Interface Operation in CQRS Model

The goal of phase 5 is to generate code from PSM-level models. Although we could have defined and executed the necessary activities for code generation in this phase, we have defined this phase as a separate process so that we can use a code generator in other projects as well and avoid the need to redefine the necessary activities for code generation in other processes. This allows us to implement a project in multiple languages using different code generators.

The code generation process consists of two phases: mapping and code generation. In the mapping phase, the concepts present in the abstract levels of PIM and PSM are mapped to a simple model at the code level. The meta-model of the defined models at the code level includes simple concepts such as file, folder, and project. In this phase, the concepts present in the PSM-level models are converted into text and stored in the defined models at the code level. The details of the code generation process is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The details of the code generation process for the experiment

Phase	Activity	Task
Mapping Phase	Map PIM & PSM Models to the Project Code Model	Map Commands to the Files in the 'Commands' Folder
		Map Events to the Files in the 'Events' Folder
		Map CommandHandlers to the Files in the 'Handlers' Folder
		Map EventHandlers to the Files in the 'Handlers' Folder
		Map Repositories Defined in CQRS Model to the Files in the 'Repositories' Folder
		Map Services Defined in CQRS Model to the Files in the 'Services' Folder
		Map ApiControllers to the Files in the 'Controllers' Folder
		Map Services Defined in Controller Model to the Files in the 'Services' Folder
		Map Entities to the Files in the 'Entities' Folder
		Map Interfaces Defined in CQRS Model to the Files in the 'Interfaces' Folder
		Map Interfaces Defined in Controller Model to the Files in the 'Interfaces' Folder
		Set Relational Dimension Between the Project Files and Class Concepts

		Set Relational Dimension Between the Project Files and Interface Concepts
Code Generation Phase	Generate C# Code	Create Project Source File
		Generate C# Code for CQRS Model
		Generate C# Code for Controller Model
		Generate C# Code for Core Domain Model
		Generate C# Code for Interfaces of CQRS Model
		Generate C# Code for Interfaces of Controller Model
		Generate Project Solution

1.2. Initial Phase: Explore Problem Domain

We use the CRAC method (Vahdati & Ramsin, 2022) to explore the problem domain. Figure 1 illustrates the CRAC metamodel used to describe this domain. Figure 2 to Figure 5, depict the online ordering system from four perspectives—order management, customer management, product management, and shopping cart management.

Figure 1: The CRAC metamodel

Figure 2: Description of order management subdomain in the form of CRAC model

Figure 3: Description of customer management subdomain in the form of CRAC model

Figure 4: Description of product management subdomain in the form of CRAC model

Figure 5: Description of shopping carts subdomain in the form of CRAC model

1.3. Construction of CIM level models

By executing transformation 1, domain objects of the DomainConcept type in the CRAC model are converted to elements of the same type in the CIM model. Next, by executing transformation 2, the responsibilities of these elements in the CRAC model become operations in the CIM model. Then the designer can define the properties of the domain objects in the CIM model using MDDPlatform facilities. At the end, by executing transformations 3 and 4, the model of domain concepts based on the Concept metamodel is produced at the CIM level.

Figure 6: CIM Construction Phase

Figure 7: CIM model (02 - Orders - CIM model)

Figure 8: CIM concepts (03- Orders – CIM Concepts)

1.4. Construction of PIM level models

Transformation 5 involves aligning the Command domain objects from the CRAC model at the CIM level with similar elements in the CQRS model at the PIM level. Transformation 6 then creates a link between command handlers and their respective commands, as well as establishing the connection between the command handler and the events that are to be emitted following the command's execution. Following this, the designer at the PIM level can determine the properties related to commands and events in the CQRS model. For each command and event handler, the designer must also define collaborators (services, interfaces, and repositories) that aid in their responsibilities. Lastly, transformations 7 and 8 are carried out to generate a detailed CQRS model at the PIM level, complete with its concepts, their properties, and operations.

When transformation 9 is carried out, it targets the domain objects within the CRAC model that manage one or more commands. This results in the creation of an ApiController domain object within the controller model, and it also identifies the commands that will handle their dispatch. Following this, transformation 10 is executed to establish an endpoint for each command. The designer then has the opportunity to define the attributes of these endpoints, such as their access route, the communication protocol and method, and whether they require authorization for access. Finally, the execution of transformation 10 yields a comprehensive controller model, delineating the concepts, their operations, and the attributes associated with each specific operation.

Through the execution of transformation 12, objects classified as DomainConcept in the CIM model are aligned with BaseEntity entities within the Core Domain model. Subsequently, transformation 13 is applied to create a RelationalDimension that links the entities at the PIM level to the domain concepts at the CIM level. Lastly, transformation 14 is carried out to develop a refined model of the core domain entities at the PIM level, providing a granular view of their structure and relationships.

Figure 9: PIM Construction Phase

Figure 10: PIM CQRS model (04- Orders – CQRS Model)

Figure 11: PIM CQRS concepts (05- Orders – CQRS Concepts)

Figure 12: PIM Controller model (06- Orders – Controller Model)

Figure 13: PIM Controller concepts (07- Orders – Controller Concepts)

Figure 14: PIM core domain model (08- Orders – Core Domain Model)

«BaseEntity.Concept» OrderItem	«BaseEntity.Concept» Order	«BaseEntity.Concept» Customer
+ Id: GuidValueObject.Concept + Name: StringValueObject.Concept + Quantity: IntegerValueObject.Concept + UnitPrice: LongValueObject.Concept + TotalPrice: LongValueObject.Concept	+ Id: GuidValueObject.Concept + OrderPrice: LongValueObject.Concept + Status: IntegerValueObject.Concept + Currency: StringValueObject.Concept + Customer: Customer + OrderItems: List<OrderItem>	+ Id: GuidValueObject.Concept + FirstName: StringValueObject.Concept + LastName: StringValueObject.Concept + Email: StringValueObject.Concept + Country: StringValueObject.Concept + Address: StringValueObject.Concept

Figure 15: PIM core domain concepts (09- Orders – Core Domain Concepts)

1.5. Construction of PSM level models

When transformation 15 is carried out, it generates a corresponding domain object within the PSM level CQRS model for every domain object at the PIM level. Following this, transformation 16 establishes a RelationalDimension that links the PSM level domain objects with the PIM level domain concepts in the CQRS model. Subsequently, the designer has the opportunity to detail certain C# implementation aspects in the PSM level CQRS model. By conducting transformation 17, which merges the domain concepts model from the PIM level with the domain objects model from the PSM level, a comprehensive CQRS model is constructed. Finally, transformations 18 through 21 are executed to define and outline the repositories and their associated interfaces.

In a manner akin to the previously described method, transformations 22 and 23 are implemented to generate the domain objects of the controller model at the PSM level, using the data from the corresponding domain objects at the PIM level. This process also establishes a RelationalDimension linkage between the PSM level domain objects and the domain concepts at the PIM level within the controller model. Subsequently, transformation 24 integrates the domain objects' data from the PSM level with the domain concepts' data from the PIM level of the controller model. Lastly, transformation 25 is executed to enrich the controller model with additional details, resulting in a more refined representation that includes domain concepts, their associated operations, and the attributes specific to each operation.

Upon completing transformation 26, the Core Domain model's domain objects are formulated at the PSM level, derived from the Core Domain model at the PIM level. Then, transformation 27 constructs a Relational Dimension connection between these PSM level domain objects and the PIM level domain concepts. Then, through transformations 28 and 29, the domain object model at

the PSM level is combined with the domain concepts of the Core Domain model at the PIM level, resulting in the addition of new details in the form of attributes.

Figure 16: PSM Construction Phase

Figure 17: PSM CQRS model – Command, CommandHandler, and Event (10- Orders – CQRS Classes)

Figure 18: PSM CQRS model - Interfaces (10- Orders – CQRS Classes)

Figure 19: PSM CQRS model – Repository operations (10- Orders – CQRS Classes)

Figure 20: PSM CQRS model concepts: Commands (11- Orders – CQRS Class Concepts)

Figure 21: PSM CQRS model concepts - Events (11- Orders – CQRS Class Concepts)

```

<<BaseClass.Concept>>
CreateOrderHandler

@ Attribute : {
  Namespace : "OnlineShop.Commands.Handlers",
  IsAbstract : "false",
  Visibility : "public",
  IsStatic : "false",
  Extend : "ICommandHandler<CreateOrder.Command.Concept>"
  using : [
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Commands",
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Brokers",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Events",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Mappers"
  ]
}

+ CreateOrderHandler(
  iorderrepository : IOrderRepository.Interface.Concept,
  icartservice : ICartService.Interface.Concept,
  icustomerservice : ICustomerService.Interface.Concept,
  imessagebroker : IMessageBroker.Interface.Concept,
  ieventmapper : IEventManager.Interface.Concept)

+ HandleAsync(createorder: CreateOrder.Command.Concept) : Task

```

```

<<BaseClass.Concept>>
CancelOrderHandler

@ Attribute : {
  Namespace : "OnlineShop.Commands.Handlers",
  IsAbstract : "false",
  Visibility : "public",
  IsStatic : "false",
  Extend : "ICommandHandler<CancelOrder.Command.Concept>"
  using : [
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Commands",
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Brokers",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Events",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Mappers"
  ]
}

+ CancelOrderHandler(
  iorderrepository : IOrderRepository.Interface.Concept,
  imessagebroker : IMessageBroker.Interface.Concept,
  ieventmapper : IEventManager.Interface.Concept)

+ HandleAsync(cancelorder: CancelOrder.Command.Concept) : Task

```

```

<<BaseClass.Concept>>
CompleteOrderHandler

@ Attribute : {
  Namespace : "OnlineShop.Commands.Handlers",
  IsAbstract : "false",
  Visibility : "public",
  IsStatic : "false",
  Extend : "ICommandHandler<CompleteOrder.Command.Concept>"
  using : [
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Commands",
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Brokers",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Events",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Mappers"
  ]
}

+ CompleteOrderHandler(
  iorderrepository : IOrderRepository.Interface.Concept,
  imessagebroker : IMessageBroker.Interface.Concept,
  ieventmapper : IEventManager.Interface.Concept)

+ HandleAsync(completeorder: CompleteOrder.Command.Concept) : Task

```

```

<<BaseClass.Concept>>
RevokeOrderHandler

@ Attribute : {
  Namespace : "OnlineShop.Commands.Handlers",
  IsAbstract : "false",
  Visibility : "public",
  IsStatic : "false",
  Extend : "ICommandHandler<RevokeOrder.Command.Concept>"
  using : [
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Commands",
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Brokers",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Events",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Mappers"
  ]
}

+ RevokeOrderHandler(
  iorderrepository : IOrderRepository.Interface.Concept,
  imessagebroker : IMessageBroker.Interface.Concept,
  ieventmapper : IEventManager.Interface.Concept)

+ HandleAsync(revokeorder: RevokeOrder.Command.Concept) : Task

```

```

<<BaseClass.Concept>>
CustomerCreatedHandler

@ Attribute : {
  Namespace : "OnlineShop.Events.Handlers",
  IsAbstract : "false",
  Visibility : "public",
  IsStatic : "false",
  Extend : "IEventHandler<CustomerCreated.Event.Concept>"
  using : [
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Events",
    "MDDPlatform.Messages.Brokers",
    "MDDPlatform.SharedKernel.Mappers"
  ]
}

+ CustomerCreatedHandler(
  icustomerrepository : ICustomerRepository.Interface.Concept)

+ HandleAsync(customercreated: CustomerCreated.Event.Concept) : Task

```

Figure 22: Figure 25: PSM CQRS model concepts – Handlers (11- Orders – CQRS Class Concepts)

Figure 23: Figure 26: Figure 25: PSM CQRS model concepts – Interfaces (11- Orders – CQRS Class Concepts)

Figure 24: PSM Controller model (12- Orders – Controller Classes)

Figure 25: PSM controller model concepts (13- Orders – Controller Class Concepts)

Figure 26: PSM core domain (14- Orders – Core Domain Classes)

Figure 27: PSM core domain concepts (15- Orders – Core Domain Class Concepts)

1.6. Construction of Code level models

Through the application of transformations 30, 31, and 32, ProjectFile type domain objects are generated at the Code level, reflecting the class definitions from the CQRS, Controller, and Core Domain models at the PSM level. Transformation 33 then establishes a RelationalDimension link between these Code level domain objects and the corresponding PSM level domain concepts. Transformation 34 initiates the creation of the .NET project file. Subsequent transformations 35, 36, and 37 merge the Code level domain objects' data with the PSM level domain concepts' information, resulting in the generation of C# class code which is then stored in the "Content" property of the ProjectFile domain objects.

This process is similarly applied to create the C# interface code. Transformations 38 and 39 lead to the creation of ProjectFile type domain objects at the Code level, based on the interface definitions in the CQRS model and the Controller. Transformation 40 forms a RelationalDimension link between these Code level objects and the PSM level domain concepts associated with the interfaces. By executing transformations 41 and 42, the Code level domain objects' information is merged with the PSM level domain concepts' information, producing the C# interface code that is saved in the "Content" property of these domain objects. Finally, transformation 43 combines the class and interface-related domain objects' information to form the solution model. MDDPlatform then uses this model to deliver the complete solution code to the user in a compressed Zip file format.

Figure 28: Code Generation Phase

Figure 29: Code level model - project dependencies (16- Orders – Project Settings & Dependencies)

Figure 30: Project file model

1.7. Model Transformation Execution in MDDPlatform

Figure 31 shows how to call and execute transformations in MDDPlatform through the cooperation of microservices.

Figure 31: Model transformations in MDDPlatform

Reference

Vahdati, A., & Ramsin, R. (2022). *Modeling and Model Transformation as a Service: Towards an Agile Approach to Model-Driven Development* (pp. 116–135). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94238-0_7